

Notes

Studies on Oxo-ions of Quinquevalent Chromium using 2-(2'-Pyridyl)-benzimidazole as a Potential Ligand

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It is known that chromium in quinquevalent state is extremely unstable in aqueous medium due to the tendency of dismutation. Thus it was the effort of the present authors to study stabilities of CrO^{3+} complexes in aqueous media. In the course of investigations on the chemistry of quinquevalent chromium, stabilisation of CrO^{3+} species in different environment, it has been observed that certain bidentate ligands¹ having the group $(\text{N}=\text{C}-\text{C}=\text{N})$ with an extended π -electron system have a profound ability to yield stable complexes with CrO^{3+} species. The ligand, 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole² having the group $(\text{N}=\text{C}-\text{C}=\text{N})$, has been used for this purpose and it has been possible to isolate compounds of Cr^{V} of marked stability performing reactions under suitable conditions in an environment of anions like Cl^- and $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ etc.

Results and Discussion

The salt $\text{LH}_2[\text{CrOCl}_3]$ and the non-electrolyte $[\text{CrOCl}_3 \cdot \text{L}]$ have been prepared by the reaction of CrO_3 in glacial acetic acid medium with concentrated hydrochloric acid and also thionyl chloride. It is interesting to note that when acetyl chloride was used instead of concentrated hydrochloric acid and thionyl chloride as reagent for conversion of Cr^{VI} to Cr^{V} , the ligand used only one of its two tertiary nitrogens for protonation and yielded the salt $(\text{LH})_2[\text{CrOCl}_3]$.

The paramagnetic oxalate $[\text{CrO}(\text{ox})\text{Cl} \cdot \text{L}]$ has been prepared by heating the non-electrolyte $[\text{CrOCl}_3 \cdot \text{L}]$ with oxalic acid in solid state at 130° in a current of dry CO_2 . Two oxo bridged compounds $[\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{L}_2]$ and $[\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3(\text{ox})_2 \cdot \text{L}_2]$ were isolated from $[\text{CrOCl}_3 \cdot \text{L}]$ and $[\text{CrO}(\text{ox})\text{Cl} \cdot \text{L}]$ by hydrolytic reaction. This hydrolytic stabilisation of Cr^{V} warrants special mention here in consideration of prevention of disproportionation of Cr^{V} to Cr^{III} and Cr^{IV} in aqueous solution which is the usual course of reaction observed by previous

authors. Thus the present work has conclusively established for the first time the hydrolytic stability of Cr^{V} using this ligand 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole.

The molar conductance values of the compounds containing $[\text{CrOCl}_3]^{2-}$ ion in acetonitrile are compatible with 1 : 1 electrolyte, while that of the others are much less than the value of 1 : 1 electrolytes³ indicating their non-electrolytic nature. The observed magnetic moments of the compounds (Sl. nos. 1-4, Table 1) correspond to spin-only value for d^1 -electron of the chromium(v) species. However, the magnetic moment values for $[\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3(\text{ox})_2 \cdot \text{L}_2]$ and $[\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{L}_2]$ suggest a spin-spin interaction through the oxygen bridges forming a dimeric structure containing $\text{Cr}-\text{O}-\text{Cr}$ and $\text{Cr} \begin{matrix} \text{O} \\ \diagdown \quad \diagup \\ \text{O} \end{matrix} \text{Cr}$ moiety.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Sl. no.	Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Oxidation state of Cr
		Cr	N	Cl	ox	
1.	$\text{LH}_2\text{CrOCl}_3$	12.10 (11.75)	9.23 (9.49)	40.69 (40.11)	—	4.9
	$\text{LH}_2\text{CrOCl}_3$ (from SOCl_2)	11.89 (11.75)	9.40 (9.49)	40.39 (40.11)	—	4.8
2.	$(\text{LH})_2\text{CrOCl}_3$	7.95 (8.15)	12.92 (13.17)	27.47 (27.84)	—	5.0
3.	$\text{CrOCl}_3 \cdot \text{L}$	14.28 (14.07)	10.96 (11.36)	28.88 (28.82)	—	5.0
4.	$\text{CrO}(\text{ox})\text{Cl} \cdot \text{L}$	13.66 (13.45)	10.52 (10.87)	9.23 (9.80)	22.69 (22.76)	5.0
5.	$\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{L}_2$	16.71 (16.53)	13.16 (13.35)	10.96 (11.28)	—	4.9
6.	$\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3(\text{ox})_2 \cdot \text{L}_2$	14.22 (14.48)	11.45 (11.69)	—	24.53 (24.51)	4.9

*L = 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole.

All the complexes exhibit a very strong doublet at $945-965\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which is attributed to the vibration of the symmetric stretching mode of the terminal $\text{Cr}=\text{O}$ bond⁴; the antisymmetric mode has not been detected. The appearance of an intense band around 750 cm^{-1} in the two dimeric complexes are attributed to the antisymmetrical bridge vibration of the $\text{Cr}-\text{O}-\text{Cr}$ moiety. The $\langle g \rangle$ values and the values of the magnetic moments (Table 2) are compatible with the values expected for d^1 -configuration of the metal with the spin-only values as the

orbital moment is quenched in a low symmetry ligand field.

The electronic spectra in acetonitrile (Table 3) clearly show the expected transitions both for the

TABLE 2—CONDUCTANCE, IR, MAGNETIC AND $\langle g \rangle$ VALUES FOR THE COMPLEXES

Sl. no.*	Compd. $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	$\nu_{\text{Cr-O}}$ cm^{-1} $\nu_{\text{Cr-O-Cr}}$ cm^{-1}	μ_{eff}^{**} B.M.	$\langle g \rangle$
1.	102.0	965	1.73 (299)	1.90
	109.5	960	1.78 (300)	1.90
2.	189.6	950	1.71 (299)	1.93
3.	59.0	960	1.70 (301)	1.93
4.	29.0	955	1.81 (300)	1.95
5.	33.8	545		
		750	0.54 (300)	-
6.	40.7	960		
		760	0.62 (300)	-

*Corresponding compound as in Table 1. **Values in parentheses indicate the temperature of measurement.

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.*	λ_{max} $K\mu$	ϵ	Assignment
1.	18.18	300	${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$
	22.22	500	${}^3B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$ ($xy \rightarrow z^2$)
	35.71	9 000	${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_2$ (I)
	41.66	12 000	${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$ (II)
	47.62	18 300	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ (Transition in LH_2^+)
2.	18.18	330	${}^3B_2 \rightarrow {}^3B_1$
	22.47	740	${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$ ($xy \rightarrow z^2$)
	33.33	11 800	${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_2$ (I)
	41.66	10 200	${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$ (II)
	45.45	18 600	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ (Transition in LH^+)
3.	16.95	135	$a_2 \rightarrow b_1^*$
	20.00	600	$a_2 \rightarrow b_2^*$
	22.73	1 300	$b_2 \rightarrow b_1^*$ ($xy \rightarrow z^2$)
	31.25	14 400	$a_2 \rightarrow a_1^*$
	41.66	15 400	$a_2 \rightarrow a_1^*$ (z^2)
	48.78	23 100	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$
4.	17.86	220	$a_2 \rightarrow b_1^*$
	21.74	810	$a_2 \rightarrow b_2^*$
	24.38	1 670	$b_2 \rightarrow b_1^*$
	31.25	17 200	$a_2 \rightarrow a_1^*$ ($xy \rightarrow x^2-y^2$)
	38.46	14 600	$a_2 \rightarrow a_1^*$ (z^2)
	50.00	22 900	$b_2 \rightarrow a_1^*$
5.	15.87	500	$a_2 \rightarrow b_1^*$
	19.61	490	$a_2 \rightarrow b_2^*$
	21.74	1 230	$b_2 \rightarrow b_1^*$
	28.57	3 600	$a_2 \rightarrow a_1^*$ ($xy \rightarrow x^2-y^2$)
	38.46	2 400	$a_2 \rightarrow a_1^*$ (z^2)
	50.00	6 000	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$
6.	19.60	360	$a_2 \rightarrow b_1^*$
	21.05	420	$b_2 \rightarrow b_2^*$
	22.47	960	$b_2 \rightarrow b_1^*$
	23.53	1 500	$a_2 \rightarrow a_1^*$ ($xy \rightarrow x^2-y^2$)
	27.00	1 200	$a_2 \rightarrow a_1^*$ (z^2)
	27.77	2 700	$b_2 \rightarrow a_1^*$

* Corresponding compound as in Table 1.

salts with C_{4v} symmetry and the other compounds with lower symmetry in the non-electrolytic complexes⁵. The hydrolytic cleavage of the 2-metal halogen bonds due to *trans*-elimination in $[\text{CrOCl}_5]^{2-}$ yielding bridged oxo-species in the Cr^V complexes have been systematically studied by the present authors.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade. Chromium was estimated iodometrically after conversion to chromate by Na_2O_2 oxidation, chloride estimated gravimetrically as AgCl , nitrogen by Duma's method and oxalate by permanganate method. Oxidation states of chromium were determined by iodometric method. Conductance was measured in acetonitrile using a dip-type cell at room temperature. Magnetic susceptibility was measured in a Gouy balance. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 599B spectrophotometer. electronic spectra (acetonitrile) on a Perkin-Elmer 550S spectrophotometer, and esr spectra (in powder form) on a Varian E-11? instrument at room temperature keeping the frequency at 9.3 GHz. Analytical data are given in Table 1 and results of conductivity measurements, magnetochemical and spectral studies are given in Tables 2 and 3.

2-(2'-Pyridyl)benzimidazolium oxopentachlorochromate(V), $LH_2[\text{CrOCl}_5]$. (a) Preparation of the salt using hydrogen chloride as reducing agent in acetic acid medium: To a solution of CrO_3 (~1 g) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml), HCl gas was passed under ice-cold condition till saturation. To the red solution thus obtained, the ligand (1.5 g) dissolved in concentrated HCl (10 ml) was added and HCl gas was passed through the solution again. The resulting bright red crystals were dried in a vacuum desiccator, (~2.0 g).

(b) Preparation of the salt using SOCl_2 : In the red solution obtained by dissolving 1 g of CrO_3 in SOCl_2 (15 ml) under ice cold conditions the ligand (1 g) (dissolved in acetic acid) was added in portions with stirring. To the red dense liquid thus obtained acetonitrile (5 ml) was added with stirring. The red crystals separated on cooling were dried in a vacuum desiccator, (1.5 g).

Di-2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazolium oxopentachlorochromate(V), $(LH)_2[\text{CrOCl}_5]$: To a solution of CrO_3 (1 g) dissolved in ice-cold acetyl chloride (20 ml), the ligand (1 g) (dissolved in acetic acid) was added and kept under ice-cold condition with occasional stirring. The resulting deep violet crystals were dried in a vacuum desiccator, (1.5 g).

Oxochloro-2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazolechromium(V), $[\text{CrOCl}_5 L]$: CrO_3 (~1 g) and the ligand (2 g) were taken in glacial acetic acid (25 ml) and through the suspended yellow mass dry HCl gas was passed under ice-cold condition until the whole mass dissolved to produce a deep red solution. On standing a chocolate brown compound separated from

the solution. The solid was dried in vacuum desiccator, (1.2 g).

Oxochloro-oxalato-2-(2'-pyridyl)chromium (v), $[CrO(ox)Cl.L]$: A mixture of powdered $CrOCl_3.L$ (~0.8 g) and oxalic acid (0.3 g) was heated at 130° in a current of dry CO_2 until evolution of HCl gas ceased. The brown coloured residue was washed with acetonitrile and dried in a vacuum desiccator, (0.7 g).

Oxo- μ -dioxodichlorobis-2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole chromium(v), $[Cr_2O_4Cl_2.L_2]$: $CrOCl_3.L$ (~1 g) was refluxed with water (20 ml) for 0.5 h. The resulting pale green coloured solid separated on cooling, dried in a vacuum desiccator, (0.8 g).

Oxo- μ -oxo-bisoxalatobis-2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazolechromium(v), $[Cr_2O_3(ox)_2.L_2]$: $CrO(ox)Cl.L$ (~1 g) was gently warmed with water (20 ml) on a water-bath during which the colour of the compound slowly changed to reddish brown. The

residue obtained on cooling was dried in a vacuum desiccator, (0.6 g).

References

1. H. K. SAHA and S. K. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, 60, 599; H. K. SAHA, S. K. GHOSH and S. S. MANDAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, 60, 985; H. K. SAHA, S. K. GHOSH and T. K. RAYCHAUDHURI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, 22, 346.
2. T. R. HARKINS, J. L. WALTER, O. E. HARRIS and H. FREISER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 260; T. J. LANE, J. NAKAGAWA, J. L. WALTER and A. J. CANDATHIL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, 1, 267.
3. W. J. GEARY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, 7, 81.
4. C. J. BARRACLOUGH, J. LEWIS and R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 3552.
5. H. B. GRAY and C. R. HARE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, 1, 363; C. D. GARNER, J. KENDRICK, P. LAMBERT, F. E. MABBS and I. H. FILLIER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, 15, 1287; O. V. ZIEBARTH and J. SELBIN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1970, 32, 939; L. G. VANQUICKENBORNE and S. P. MCGLYNN, *Theor. Chem. Acta*, 1963, 2, 393.